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Control of Clec7a by HPV E6.

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We measured total transcription in cells over-expressing the papillomavirus E6 gene that has described functions in binding and inactivation of p53 for discovery of novel E6 associated cellular functions. We demonstrate here control of Clec7a by HPV E6. This was a conserved property of HPV E6 across type: for both HPV16 E6 and for HPV84 E6.

Citations

1. Jian, J.X., Yin, X.Y., Mei, X.D., Yang, J.J., Ji, M.H. and Shen, J.C., 2026. Clec7a Drives Microglial Activation–Mediated Myelin Degradation in Sepsis-Associated Encephalopathy. *Inflammation*.

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